

Comparative study of Cd-free Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells with amorphous In₂O₃:H and ZnO:Al front contact layers.

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Supplementary information

Figure S1: (a) Transmittance and reflectance spectra for ZnO:Al (AZO) and In₂O₃:H (IOH) on top of soda-lime glass (SLG). Sigmoid-Boltzmann fitting for the complete absorbance as a function of energy for the (b) AZO and (c) IOH thin films.

Figure S2: (a) Raman spectra and (b) XRD patterns for CdS- and ZTO-based solar cells with ZnO:Al (AZO) and In₂O₃:H (IOH) front contact layers. The dotted lines correspond to the Raman spectra of the samples without the window layers.

Table S1: Solar cell parameters of the champion solar cells.

Parameter	CdS/AZO	CdS/IOH	ZTO/AZO	ZTO/IOH
J_{sc} [mA cm^{-2}]	32	30	30	30
V_{oc} [mV]	627	633	602	607
FF [%]	72	72	64	62
PCE [%]	14	13.5	12	11.5
Series resistance [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]	0.9	1.8	2	3.3
Shunt resistance [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]	1197	1125	469	460

Table S2 Average solar cell parameters of all samples.

Parameter	CdS/AZO	CdS/IOH	ZTO/AZO	ZTO/IOH
J_{sc} [mA cm^{-2}]	31 ± 2	27 ± 1	29 ± 2	28 ± 2
V_{oc} [mV]	624 ± 9	625 ± 6	595 ± 10	605 ± 9
FF [%]	65 ± 6	69 ± 2	56 ± 5	61 ± 2
PCE [%]	13 ± 1	11.6 ± 0.8	10 ± 1	10.2 ± 0.7
Series resistance [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]	1.4 ± 0.7	2.5 ± 0.4	3 ± 1	4.3 ± 0.7
Shunt resistance [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]	847 ± 341	990 ± 246	270 ± 159	494 ± 50

Figure S3: (a) Internal quantum efficiency (IQE) and (b) reflectance spectra for the CdS- and ZTO-based solar cells with ZnO:Al (AZO) and $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3:\text{H}$ (IOH) as front contact layers.

Figure S4: Solar cell parameters for CdS- and ZTO-based devices with ZnO:Al (AZO) and In₂O₃:H (IOH) front contact layers before and after a 30-minute light soaking treatment: (a) power conversion efficiency (PCE), (b) short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), (c) fill factor (FF), and (d) open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}).